

The mean values obtained are $K_1 = 3.1 \times 10^{-2}$ and $K_2 = 2.2 \times 10^{-3}$ at 35° . These values, though of the same order as in the present work, are materially different in magnitude, being about half of those latter. A few experiments on the determination of freezing points of dilute lead propionate solutions by the present authors indicate that the values of K_1 and K_2 , found in this paper, agree better with the freezing point data as compared to the values obtained by Mohanty and Aditya (*loc. cit.*). The details of the cryoscopic work will be published later.

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SOME ALIPHATIC MONOCARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES OF BIVALENT METALS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART IV. COBALT MONO-ACETATO COMPLEX

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The composition of the complex formed between Co^{2+} and acetate ions has been found to be CoAc^+ from a study of the equilibrium H^+ ion concentrations in mixtures of equimolecular cobalt nitrate and acetic acid solutions, by "Job's method of continued variation", using a new index property, viz., the increase of H^+ ion concentration.

The thermodynamic dissociation constant, K , for the equilibrium $\text{CoAc}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Co}^{2+} + \text{Ac}^-$ has been found out as 37.2×10^{-3} at 29.31° , by the direct application of "law of mass action", taking into account the activity coefficients of the individual ions, calculated from the ionic strength of the mixture of cobalt nitrate and acetic acid solutions employing the "Debye-Hückel limiting law".

Thermodynamic dissociation constant, K , for the equilibrium, $(\text{CoAc})^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Co}^{2+} + \text{Ac}^-$

$$K = \frac{a_{\text{Co}^{2+}} \cdot a_{\text{Ac}^-}}{a_{\text{CoAc}^+}} = \frac{c_{\text{Co}^{2+}} \cdot c_{\text{Ac}^-}}{c_{\text{CoAc}^+}} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{Co}^{2+}} \cdot f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{f_{\text{CoAc}^+}}$$

has been determined by following the same procedure as adopted for lead acetato complex described in Part I of this series (*this Journal*, 1958, 35, 269) from the determination of p_{H} of solution mixtures, containing a volume '1-x' of cobalt nitrate and 'x' of acetic acid, 'x' varying between 0.1 and 0.9, and both parent solutions being at concentration C. The composition of the complex formed has been determined as in the case of lead acetato complex (*loc. cit.*) by the application of "Job's method of continued variation", using the increase, 'Y', of

the H^+ ion concentration in the mixture, over the sum of H^+ concentrations of the parent solutions at the same dilution as the index property. From the plots of 'Y' against 'x', it has been observed that the maximum value of 'Y' corresponds to the reacting proportion 1:1 for cobalt nitrate and acetic acid, and this shows that under the condition of the experiment the equilibrium,

is most prominent, and the chance of the formation of higher complexes like $CoAc_2$, $CoAc_3^-$ etc. is negligible.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cobalt nitrate and acetic acid used were of A.R. quality. All solutions were prepared with conductivity water. Stock solutions of cobalt nitrate and acetic acid at concentrations slightly higher than the desired value, 'C', were prepared, and in the solutions cobalt was determined gravimetrically as sulphate, and acetic acid was estimated by titration with a standard alkali solution. Then these were brought to the desired concentration 'C' by proper dilution with conductivity water. All solution mixtures shown in the tables were prepared from these parent solutions.

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TABLE I

(After keeping the mixtures in a closed room for 3 hrs., the p_H values were determined by the method described in Part III, p. 323).

(HAc stands for acetic acid)

1-x.	Solution mixtures studied.			Conc. of parent solns. (M/5). C=0.2; p=1; Temp.=31°.		Conc. of parent solns. (M/3). C=0.333; p=1; Temp.=29°.	
	HAc.	Cobalt nitrate.	Water.	p_H .	Increase in $[H^+]$, ($Y \times 10^4$).	p_H .	Increase in $[H^+]$, ($Y \times 10^4$).
0.10	9 c.c.	1 c.c.	...	2.549	14.86	2.414	21.791
	9	...	1 c.c.	2.99			
	...	1	9	3.50			
0.20	8	2	...	2.461	21.04	2.274	36.723
	8	...	2	3.00			
	...	2	8	3.45			
0.30	7	3	...	2.404	24.37	2.116	47.181
	7	...	3	3.03			
	...	3	7	3.24			
0.40	6	4	...	2.38	26.81	2.127	58.032
	6	...	4	3.06			
	...	4	6	3.21			
0.45	5.5	4.5	...	2.363	28.38	2.088	64.583
	5.5	...	4.5	3.07			
	...	4.5	5.5	3.19			

TABLE I (contd.)

$r-x$	HAc.	Cobalt nitrate.	Water.	p_H .	Conc. of parent soln.	p_H .	Conc. of parent solns.
0.50	5	5	...	2.351	29.49	2.077	66.107
	5	...	5	3.08		2.99	
	...	5	5	3.17		3.13	
0.55	4.5	5.5	...	2.369	27.22	...	...
	4.5	...	5.5	3.09		...	
	...	5.5	4.5	3.13		...	
0.60	4	6	...	2.385	24.64	2.09	62.175
	4	...	6	3.11		3.03	
	...	6	4	3.06		3.01	
0.65	3.5	6.5	...	2.382	25.00	2.084	62.980
	3.5	...	6.5	3.12		3.06	
	...	6.5	3.5	3.05		2.97	
0.70	3	7	...	2.392	23.76	2.077	64.057
	3	...	7	3.14		3.10	
	...	7	3	3.02		2.93	
0.75	2.5	7.5	...	2.41	22.29	2.093	60.544
	2.5	...	7.5	3.18		3.12	
	...	7.5	2.5	3.00		2.90	
0.80	2	8	...	2.438	19.55	2.112	57.323
	2	...	8	3.19		3.19	
	...	8	2	2.98		2.87	
0.90	1	9	...	2.513	14.22	2.207	42.072
	1	...	9	3.28		3.23	
	...	9	1	2.95		2.85	

TABLE II

The symbols used in the table headings and their evaluations are same as in Part I (*loc. cit.*) of the series.

$r-x$	Solution mixtures.		Conc. of parent soln. ($M/5$). $C=0.2$; $p=1$; Temp. = 31° .		Conc. of parent soln. ($M/3$). $C=0.333$; $p=1$; Temp. = 29° .	
	HAc. soln.	Cobalt nitrate soln.	Ionic strength (μ).	$K \times 10^3$.	Ionic strength (μ).	$K \times 10^3$.
0.10	9 c.c.	1 c.c.	0.0594	3.53	0.0987	3.59
0.20	8	2	0.1181	2.09	0.1962	1.39
0.30	7	3	0.1773	1.33	0.2945	0.738
0.40	6	4	0.2368	0.96	0.3930	0.382
0.45	5.5	4.5	0.2685	0.76	0.4423	0.264
0.50	5.0	5.0	0.2963	0.62	0.4918	0.209
0.55	4.5	5.5	0.3264	0.59	...	...
0.60	4.0	6.0	0.3565	0.54	0.5918	0.150
0.65	3.5	6.5	0.3864	0.44	0.6417	0.114
0.70	3.0	7.0	0.4164	0.36	0.6913	0.083
0.75	2.5	7.5	0.4465	0.31	0.7417	0.066
0.80	2.0	8.0	0.4767	0.25	0.7917	0.049
0.90	1.0	9.0	0.5371	0.13	0.8930	0.021

N.B. The ionisation constant of acetic acid (HAc) at the temperature of the experiment ($29-31^\circ$) has been taken to be $K_a = 1.75 \times 10^{-5}$ (Harned and Owen, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", 2nd. ed., p. 580).

The results of p_R measurements for mixtures of the parent solutions of cobalt

FIG. 2

* Solar sign represents the plot of pK_2 against $\sqrt{\mu_{\text{mean}}}$ for Part V of this series (this issue, p. 343).

work on the subject, as also comment on the present work will be made in Part V of this series.

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nitrate and acetic acid, both at concentration $C=0.2M$ and also both at concentration $C=0.333M$, have been shown in Table I. The curves I and II in Fig. 1 represent the plots Y against x , from the data in Table I for $C=0.2M$ and that for $C=0.333M$ respectively. The values of ' μ ' and ' K ' for the solution mixtures have been obtained by adopting the same procedure as described in Part I of this series (*loc. cit.*), and are shown in Table II. Here also, like the case of lead acetate complex (Part I, *loc. cit.*), the plot ' K ' against ' μ ' from Table II yields a smooth curve, which, however, has not been used to evaluate the value of ' K ' by extrapolation to zero ionic strength. The graph pK ($-\log K$) against ' $\sqrt{\mu}$ ' represented in Fig. 2 gives a straight line curve, which on extrapolation to " $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ " leads to the value of pK corresponding to the true thermodynamic constant ' K '. These values of pK and K at " $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ " are 1.52 and 30.2×10^{-3} at 29-31° respectively.

Critical review on the previous

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